

“THE HISTORY OF THE MEMORIAL HOUSE-MUSEUM DEDICATED TO THE MEMORY OF SULAIMON YUDAKOV”

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ABSTRACT

This article highlights the life and creative activity of Sulaimon Yudakov, one of the prominent representatives of Uzbek musical art, as well as the activities of the memorial house-museum associated with his name. The composer's contribution to the development of national music, his works, and the cultural heritage preserved in the museum are analyzed. Special attention is also given to the scientific, educational, and cultural significance of the museum.

Uzbek national musical art has a centuries-old history, and many talented composers have played an important role in its development. Among them, Suleiman Yudakov occupies a special place as a major representative of 20th-century Uzbek music. He not only continued national musical traditions but also enriched them with new genres and styles. Today, his rich creative heritage is widely promoted through the memorial house-museum. This museum serves not only as a place where exhibits are preserved but also as a scientific and cultural center.

Suleiman Alexandrovich Yudakov was born on April 14, 1916, in the city of Kokand, into a Bukharian Jewish family. In his youth, he went through severe life hardships, becoming an orphan at the age of twelve and growing up in a children's home in Kokand. It was there that his interest in music was formed, and he began to study music systematically for the first time. He learned musical notation and mastered playing instruments such as the balalaika, mandolin, guitar, and wind instruments. One of his first teachers was Mikhail Genrikhovich Naygof [1; 608].

In 1932, Suleiman Yudakov entered the music faculty of the P. I. Tchaikovsky Conservatory in Moscow, where he studied in the flute class. Later, in 1939, he continued his studies in the composition department under the guidance of the famous composer R. M. Glière. In 1941, due to the outbreak of World War II, he had to interrupt his studies and returned to Tashkent.

From 1941, Yudakov was mainly engaged in creative activity. In 1943–1944, he worked as an artistic director at the Tajikistan Philharmonic [2; 303]. His творчество (creative work)

is distinguished by the combination of Uzbek and Tajik folk melodies with modern musical styles, diversity of genres, and the brightness of melodies.

In 1944, Suleiman Yudakov composed the music for the anthem of the Tajik SSR. This melody later served as the basis for the national anthem of the independent Republic of Tajikistan. In 1945, he created the musical drama “Offspring”

In the post-war years, the composer’s творчество reached a new level, and he created many major works. Among them are “Poem of the East” for violin and piano, “Fantasy for violin, cello, and piano,” and “Dance Suite” for two pianos. The “Dance Suite” consists of three parts: “Khorezm Festival March,” “Azerbaijani Lyric Dance,” and “Fergana Dance.”

In 1958, Suleiman Yudakov created the first Uzbek comic opera — “Maysara’s Affair,” which became an important event in Uzbek musical art. This opera was staged in 1959 at the Alisher Navoi Theater and achieved great success. The work was translated into nine languages and staged in cities such as Tashkent, Samarkand, Moscow, Lodz (Poland), Ashgabat, Dushanbe, Bishkek, and Ufa.

In 1967, he created another significant work — the first Uzbek comic ballet “The Youth of Nasriddin.” In addition, the composer is the author of the ballet “Living Flame,” cantatas such as “My Homeland,” “Congratulations,” “Alyor,” the vocal-symphonic suite “Mirzachul,” as well as many vocal-symphonic poems, songs, and romances [3; 291].

Yudakov’s songs such as “Friends,” “Circle Song,” “My Uzbekistan,” and “Carnival Waltz” became widely popular among the people. He also composed music for dramatic performances and films. His творчество was highly appreciated by the state: in 1951 he received the State Prize, and in 1977 he was awarded the Hamza State Prize of Uzbekistan.

The works he created became part of the treasury of Uzbek national culture. S. Yudakov is one of the founders of new genres in national musical art, such as romance, piano duet, quartet, and cantata [4; 179]. He wrote the first Uzbek comic opera “Maysara’s Tricks” and the satirical-comedic ballet “The Youth of Nasriddin.” Yudakov also created works such as “My Native Land,” “Mirzachul,” “Carnival Waltz,” a romance based on A. S. Pushkin’s poem “Do not sing of beauty before my eyes,” and “Friends.” All of these are reflected in the museum exhibition opened in the house of the Union of Composers of Uzbekistan, where the great Uzbek composer lived and worked for many years.

The museum was opened on December 14, 2018, with the support of the Union of Composers of Uzbekistan, the Tashkent Foundation bearing his name, as well as the efforts of his colleagues and friends. The main objectives of the museum are to conduct scientific research in the field of culture and art, organize scientific conferences, creative evenings, and concerts, publish informational materials, monographs, books, and albums, as well as prepare video and audio materials and discs.

Significant work has been carried out to analyze manuscript materials that represent the museum’s greatest value. The museum houses S. Yudakov’s earliest romances and songs in manuscript form, musical scores, recordings, published works, and personal correspondence. Among the exhibits, the most valuable items are the musical recordings, gramophone records, and published scores of the first performances of the opera “Maysara’s Tricks,” performed with the participation of People’s Artist of Uzbekistan Khalima Nosirova [5; 100].

The museum regularly hosts literary seminars by young writers led by Alexey Ustimenko, meetings of the “Maysara” creative club [4; 180], gatherings with prominent cultural figures, and sessions of the “Danko” literary and creative association. Meetings with composers and musicians are also held on a regular basis.

Suleiman Yudakov is one of the composers who made an invaluable contribution to the development of Uzbek musical art. The works he created have become an integral part of our national culture. The memorial house-museum plays an important role in preserving his name and passing his creative legacy on to future generations. Through the museum’s activities, not only the composer’s творчество but also musical culture in general is widely promoted. This, in turn, is of great importance for the development and preservation of national art.

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